

THE LEGEND OF LAZGI AND ITS HISTORY

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Abstract. This article discusses the history of Lazgi, the types of "Lazgi" dance that have survived to this day.

Keywords: Lazgi, history, dance, music, dress.

ЛЕГЕНДА О ЛЯЗГИ И ЕЕ ИСТОРИЯ

Аннотация. В этой статье рассматривается история лязги, виды танца «лязги», сохранившиеся до наших дней.

Ключевые слова: лязги, история, танец, музыка, одежда.

"Lazgi" is an ancient ritual pattern that has survived from pre-Islamic times to our days. According to experts, this three-part composition reflects resurrection, empowerment, and death.

In an interview with Ozodlik, musicologist and professor of the Faculty of Fine Arts at Ardahan University in Turkey, Botir Matyokubov said that "Lazgi" is a "men's war dance."

"There is evidence that this is a 6/8 time battle dance. In musical measures and methods, the 6/8 time is danceable and energetic in all nations, and this method is followed by expressions such as "Gul ufori", in Khorezm in the folk language "Tandira kasak", in Bukhara "Chilligi or Chillaki", and in Tashkent-Fergana - "Umbalaqidon-Lakkalaqidon". If we analyze the musical motifs of "Lazgi" (especially "Surnay lazgi"), we will see that some parts of the dance tunes of the era of Khusravani, that is, the ancient musicologist Barbad, resemble the "Mavrigi" ones.

In the article "Lazgi" by the late musicologist from Khorezm, Sofia Sobirova, published in the magazine "Yoshlik" in 1983, there is information that "during one of the Caucasian campaigns of the soldiers of Khorezmshah Jalolidin Manguberdi, the mehtars (music company - ed.) played the battle dance "Lazgi" and the warriors joined in the game." In the past, "Lazgi" were mainly dance tunes played on instruments, and words were not composed and sung to them. However, by the 30s of the 20th century, it was observed that they were included in folk poems and sung.

According to Mangitli Tursun Bakhshi, a circle player named Otaq daqa-daqa used to sing the "Lazgi afsonasi" (The Legend of Lazgi) and then the "Jon tana gir" (Life, body, soul) rhymed poem at weddings and receptions. After him, until the 1950s, the harmonist Khoja Otajonov-Khoja kor (the father of Ortiq Otajonov's circle player Kadam Khoja - ed.) used to sing the "Shabboz melon torlama, Gurlan yolin yollama, gizyumuga er galdik, uka biznes khorlama" (Don't tie the melon to the tree, don't let the road roar, we've only just arrived home, brother, don't humiliate us).

From this period, the "Lazgi" dance, sung by Komil Khorezmi to the theme "Whom do you love?", became popular throughout Central Asia.

To this day, about nine types of "Lazgi" dance have survived.

The history of the "Lazgi" dance, which is set to music created by the striking of stones, is said to date back to the Stone Age.

There are various types of "Lazgi" in Khorezm, the oldest of which are "Surnay Lazgi", "Dutor Lazgi", "Kairok Lazgi". The following are "Changak Lazgi", "Garmon Lazgi", "Bodya (tavoq) Lazgi" and others.

"Lazgi" - reflects the renewal, resurrection, and the fact that paralysis has given life to the body. After the death of Karimov, the leader of the "new Uzbekistan" that began to revive, took the initiative to establish a "Lazgi" academy in Khorezm.

In March 2020, Shavkat Mirziyoyev proposed holding an international festival of "Lazgi" in Khorezm.

Gavhar Matyokubova is a representative of the second generation of female dancers in Khorezm. It is known that her teachers, Rovia Otajonova, Anash Khalfa Sobirova (Anash Choloq) and Tamarakhonim, learned to dance "Lazgi" from male teachers. According to Gavhar Matyokubova, "until the 7th century, everyone danced "Lazgi":

"After the establishment of Islamic ideology in Khorezm in the 7th century, women were forbidden to dance by a fatwa of scholars. Only men were allowed. From the 7th century until 1920, only men danced. In 1920, Anash Choloq Sobirova (whose leg was broken because she danced. ed.) first danced "Lazgi." When Tamarakhanim arrived in Khorezm in 1932, she was taught "Lazgi" by men. Masters such as Jummi Kairok, Bobojon Toq Toq, and Zarif Latipov taught the "Lazgi" dance to women. The Khorezm lazgi has a three-thousand-year history. Doctor of Philology, associate professor of the Uzbek State Academy of Choreography, Hulkar Hamroyeva, told Sputnik about the history of this dance and interesting information about it.

According to him, the Lazgi dance is like a diamond. No matter which way you look at it, new facets are revealed, and there was no black dress in the Lazgi.

Women dancing the Lazgi mainly wear bright colors. For example, older women danced in the "Dutor" lazgi. They had a lachak on their heads. Young girls had feathers on their heads. Their clothes were mainly decorated with coins. Men danced with a turban on their heads. The "Surnay" lazgi was mainly a men's dance and was also called a heroic dance during the time of the Khorezmshahs.

The associate professor of the State Academy of Choreography said that one of the dances similar to the Khorezm dance is the Lezginka dance. This is due to the Khorezmshahs' campaigns in the Caucasus. It can be said with certainty that the roots of the Lezginka began with the Lazgi.

"If you pay attention, the Lazgi has a mood and enthusiasm that lifts a person's spirits. In addition, the dance is associated with the Avesta period. That is why "Lazgi" is included in the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity as an element of the cultural heritage of Uzbekistan," Hamrayeva emphasized. Masters of art such as Gavhar Matoqubova, Tamarakhonim, and Mukarrama Turgunbayeva brought Khorezm folk dances to perfection. The analysis of Khorezm dances by Gavhar Matoqubova in connection with national values and ethnography is a unique phenomenon not only in Uzbek, but also in world choreographic art.

Detailed information about Khorezm dance is provided in books such as "Ofatijon Lazgi", "Lazgi Monograph", and recently published in Uzbek and English "History and Description of Khorezm Lazgi Dance". The international dance festival "Lazgi" will be held in the city of Khiva, Khorezm region. Representatives of more than 30 countries will participate in the festival. Representatives of dance ensembles and experts from various delegations from Great Britain, Russia, Turkey, Bulgaria, Iran, Azerbaijan, Tajikistan arrived in Tashkent yesterday to participate in the event.

According to the guests, this festival will be a great opportunity to learn more about Uzbek dances and demonstrate the dance art of the countries. Experts plan to include Uzbek dances in their repertoire.

An international scientific and practical conference will also be held as part of the festival. The director of the Center for Uzbek Language and Culture in Moscow will participate in it with a presentation (online) entitled "Promotion of Khorezm Lazgi Dance in Russia". It is worth noting that currently in Moscow there are groups "Feruz" and "Sanata" that are studying Uzbek dance. Cooperation has been established between them and the State Academy of Choreography of Uzbekistan.

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